

Synthesis and antibacterial activity of nickel(II), zinc(II) and copper(II) complexes with 2-(thiomethyl-2'-benzimidazolyl)-1,3-diazacyclopentadec- Δ' -ene

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Six-coordinated Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes have been prepared by one-pot synthesis using metal acetates, 2-chloromethylbenzimidazole (L₁) and 2-mercapto-1,3-diazacyclopentadec- Δ' -ene (L₂). Ligands and complexes have been evaluated for their antibacterial activity.

Imidazole ring as a part of histidine moiety and benzimidazole ring as well as its methyl derivative functions as ligand towards transition metal ions in a variety of biologically important molecules including iron-heme systems, vitamin B-12 and its derivatives as well as in several other metalloproteins¹. Additionally, the macrocyclic thiourea (2-mercapto-1,3-diazacyclopenta-dec- Δ' -ene) is bioactive² possessing hydrophobic groups. In view of this, we found it worthwhile to condense both the biologically important components in the presence of most common metal ions of bio-importance like Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} in anticipation that they may impart their easy penetration to the cell membrane owing to their greater lipophilicity³ hence serving as better candidates for bioactivity.

Results and Discussion

One pot synthesis of the metal complexes was made by the condensation of both the components L₁ and L₂ together with the metal acetates. However, ligand L initially prepared by the condensation of L₁ and L₂ could also be complexed with the metal acetates yielding the similar product.

The complexes were found to be insoluble in most of the common solvents except DMSO in which they were partially soluble, whereas Zn^{II} complex showed better solubil-

ity. The electronic spectra and cyclic voltammogram (CV) were therefore recorded in solid state. Their molar conductance however could not be recorded. The elemental analysis of the complexes (Table 1) corresponds to their compositions, [Cu₂L(OAc)₄].2H₂O and [M.L(OAc)₂].2H₂O (M = Ni^{II}/Zn^{II}).

Table 1 Elemental and spectral data for the metal complexes

Compound	Metal %	μ_{eff} B M	λ_{max} (nm)
	Found (Calcd)		
[Ni L (OAc) ₂].4H ₂ O	10.1 (9.4)	2.9	258, 297, 326, 449, 685
[Cu ₂ L (OAc) ₄].2H ₂ O	17.1 (16.5)	3.1	260, 296, 326, 399, 490, 690
[Zn L (OAc) ₂].2H ₂ O	11.2 (11.0)	Diamag	260, 296, 326, 445

Ir spectra : The ligand (L) $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ band at 1560 cm⁻¹ for L₂ (macrocyclic part) underwent lower shift to 1520 cm⁻¹ in the Cu^{II} complex indicating coordination with the Cu^{II} ion. However, its position remained unchanged in the Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes showing its non-participation in coordination with these metal ions. Furthermore, $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ from L₁ (benzimidazolyl part) observed in the free ligand at 1480 cm⁻¹ shifted to 1453, 1452 and 1441 cm⁻¹ in the Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes, respectively, indicating its involvement in the coordination. Additionally, the ligand (L) band observed at 720 cm⁻¹ (C-S) shifted to 745 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes showing its participation in coordination with the metal ions. Peaks due to ν_{asym} and ν_{sym} (CH₃COO⁻) were observed at ~1626, 1575; 1608, 1580 and 1624, 1575 cm⁻¹ in the Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes respectively, indicating coordination of CH₃COO⁻ in the complexes⁴. Poor resolution of the spectra at lower energy region restricted us to identify $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ peaks.

¹H nmr spectra : The free ligand peak observed at δ 4.0 due to =N-CH₂ protons were found at δ 3.94 in the spectra

of the Zn^{II} complexes, indicating its non-participation through nitrogen atom of this group with the Zn^{II} ion. Furthermore, there was no change in the aromatic peaks but the peak due to $S-CH_2$ protons observed at δ 3.6 in free ligand shifted to higher field at δ 3.2 in case of the Zn^{II} complex, most likely due to the coordination of its sulphur with Zn^{II} ion.

Electronic spectra : Electronic spectral data of the complexes are shown in Table 1. The electronic spectrum of the Ni^{II} complex showed two bands at 685 and 450 nm assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively. The band at 449 nm was considered to overlap with the $M \rightarrow L$ charge transfer peak in view of the peak position observed in similar region (445 nm) in the spectrum of the Zn^{II} complex. In the Cu^{II} complex, however a broad band observed at 690 nm suggested octahedral geometry in view of the earlier report⁵. The remaining band positions were found to be very close to intra-ligand peaks reported in the literature⁵.

Magnetic moment : Room temperature magnetic moment observed for $[Cu_2.L.OAc)_4].2H_2O$ (3.1 B.M.) indicated lowering in magnetic moment value. The variable temperature magnetic moment values recorded for the same complex, however, showed very little change in the values at higher temperatures 0.005×10^{-2} e.m.u. at $+50^\circ$ to 0.03×10^{-2} e.m.u. at $+150^\circ$ as compared to data recorded at lower temperatures 0.015×10^{-2} e.m.u. at -50° to 0.018×10^{-2} e.m.u. at -150° .

Electrochemical studies : Due to restricted solubility of the complexes in different solvents, cyclic voltammogram (CV) of the complex $[Cu_2.L.OAc)_4].2H_2O$ was recorded by coating the working platinum electrode with metal complex using Triton X 100 as binder in acetonitrile solution. The CV (Fig. 1) showed metal based broad oxidation peak at 1.04 V with the corresponding broad reduction peak at 0.7 V. The weak initial oxidation observed at 0.06 V without the corresponding reduction peak could arise from ligand part. The quasireversible oxidation peak at 1.04 V may be due to conversion of Cu^{II} to Cu^{III} state which in turn gets reduced to Cu^{III}/Cu^{II} . No ligand (L_1 and L_2) based peaks were observed under the potential range studied.

Antibacterial activity : The ligands L_1 , L_2 , hydrated metal acetates as well as their metal complexes were tested by the poisoned food technique⁶. Required amounts of the compounds were dissolved separately in 1% Tween 80 (0.5 ml) and then mixed with melted sterile nutrient agar medium (10 ml) and inoculated. The plates were incubated at 37° .

The bacterial growth inhibition measured after 24 h

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of the complex $[Cu_2(L).(OAc)_4].2H_2O$ in acetonitrile (10^{-3} mol dm^{-3}) using $NaClO_4$ (0.1 mol dm^{-3}) supporting electrolyte and Ag/Ag^+ as reference electrode at room temperature and at 250 mV/s.

against bacteria *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella* at 100, 500 and 1000 ppm concentration showed that ligand L_1 was active at 500 ppm and 1000 ppm while ligand L_2 was slightly active at these concentrations. However, $[Zn.L.(OAc)_2].2H_2O$ was found significantly active at 100 ppm and highly active i.e. showed no growth of bacteria at 500 ppm. Furthermore, antibacterial activity of $[Zn.L.(OAc)_2].2H_2O$ was also studied at minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) 50, 100, 200 and 300 ppm against *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella* sp., *Vibrio cholerae*, *Pseudomonas* sp., *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Micrococcus sedentarius* 7B5, *Acinetobacter* sp. H5DC1 and *Staphylococcus intermedius* 6146. At MIC 200 ppm the Zn^{II} complex was found active against all the bacteria except *Pseudomonas* sp. However, this complex showed no growth of even most resistive bacteria⁷ like *Pseudomonas* sp. at 300 ppm concentration. Thus, the complex $[Zn.L.(OAc)_2].2H_2O$ showed a broad range of antibacterial activity inhibiting all the bacteria studied.

Experimental

2-Chloromethylbenzimidazole (L_1) and 2-mercapto-1,3-diazacyclopenta-dec- Δ' -ene (L_2) were prepared using reported procedure^{2,8}. All chemicals and solvents used were of A.R. grade (E. Merck) and used as such.

The metals were estimated following standard procedures⁹. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Cahn-Faraday electrobalance using $Hg[Co(NCS)_4]$ as calibrant and diamagnetic correction was applied using Pascal's constant¹⁰. Ir (KBr), 1H nmr (DMSO- d_6) and electronic (nujol) spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 783 FTIR, Jeol FX 90Q FT NMR and Cary 23 spectrometers respectively. The variable temperature magnetic moment was recorded at U.S.I.C., University of Roorkee, India.

The ligand L was initially prepared by the condensation of L₁ and L₂ using reported procedure¹¹. A mixture of 2-chloromethylbenzimidazole (0.01 mol) and 2-mercapto-1,3-diazacyclopenta-dec-Δ'-ene (0.01 mol) in pyridine (10 ml) containing few drops of Et₃N was heated on a water-bath for about 4 h. After cooling for 24 h, the solution was poured into ice-cold water (100 ml). The resulting yellow solid was washed with water, crystallized from a mixture of DMF-ethanol (2 : 1) and dried under reduced pressure (yield 30%), m.p. 170°.

Metal complexes : In the general procedure used for the preparation of the metal complexes, a mixture of ligand L₁ (0.01 mol), the respective metal acetate (0.01 mol) taken in methanol (10 ml) and a few drops of Et₃N was stirred for 1 h. Then a solution of ligand L₂ (0.01 mol) in methanol (5 ml) was added to it and stirred again for 1 h followed by refluxing for 12 h. It was cooled and stored for 24 h in a refrigerator. The resulting solid was washed with water and ethanol, and dried under reduced pressure (50–60%), m.p. >300°.

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